

101034439 - REsolution

Medical Genetic Solutions for RESOLUTE

**WP5 – Project management,
dissemination of results and
ethics requirements**

D5.5 DEP first revision accepted by the GA

Lead contributor	Alvaro Ingles-Prieto (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)
	ainglesprieto@cemm.at
Other contributors	Tabea Wiedmer (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences)

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1. Abstract

To ensure that REsolution project results will be optimally disseminated and exploited, the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) is i) describing the actions, strategies and channels that will maximise the impact of the project, ii) including the internal procedures of notification and agreements for efficient sharing of REsolution data and resources; and iii) ensuring that promotional material, publications, biological tools, posters, oral presentations will be disseminated as widely as possible.

2. Key message

Solute carriers (SLCs) are transport proteins located on cellular membranes and can be seen as cellular “gates”. With more than 400 proteins, they constitute the largest family of transporters in the human genome and represent a largely untapped source of potential novel drug targets. They are essential for a cell’s well-being and often genetically associated with human diseases – such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), autism, Alzheimer’s disease, schizophrenia, diabetes, metabolic and cardiovascular diseases, and several types of cancer – and play an integral role in drug absorption into specific organs.

REsolution aims at gathering publicly available datasets and combining them with novel experimental data on genetic variants of SLCs associated with human diseases. To that end, REsolution will build on the ongoing IMI project RESOLUTE, which is working efficiently on a systematic campaign to increase the knowledge on SLCs by creating tools and datasets and making them available to the scientific community.

REsolution will follow an “open-access ethos” and it will deliver novel publicly accessible research reagents, techniques, datasets and knowledge to both the biochemical and the clinical research communities. To ensure the sustainability of the research reagents and data generated by REsolution, we will make them accessible *via* public repositories (e.g. Addgene for plasmids, ENA for sequencing data). Novel techniques, protocols and standard operation procedures will be published in open access (gold) journals or deposited in the RESOLUTE website. The knowledge and datasets generated in REsolution will be assimilated and integrated into the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, which combines public datasets with RESOLUTE-generated datasets on all human SLCs. Ultimately, the outcome of both projects together will rapidly accelerate the pace of research in SLCs, as well as the understanding of their role in human diseases.

3. Communication objectives

The main REsolution communication objectives are to:

- Enhance the visibility of the REsolution project and SLC research on a local, national and international level.
- Establish the RESOLUTE web portal – which will integrate REsolution output – as the leading hub for clinicians and biochemical researchers where to gain access to resources, data and knowledge on SLCs and their association to human diseases.
- Attract the interest of potential future partners, neighbouring networks and initiatives.
- Encourage talented students and young scientists to engage in the science of SLCs.
- Draw the attention of national governments, regional authorities and other public and private funding sources to the need for and ultimate benefits of the REsolution research activities.
- Pave the way for market demand for the products or services to be developed in the long-term based on the project results.
- Increase the awareness on SLCs involved in disease to make them attractive targets for new drug discovery campaigns.

4. Target audiences

Key audiences and potential stakeholders include:

- Academic and research organizations
- Clinicians and patient organizations
- SLC / membrane transporters scientific community
- General scientific community
- EFPIA members and other pharmaceutical companies
- Biotech SMEs involved in small-molecule drug discovery and technology development
- Drug policy makers (e.g. EMA and FDA)
- The general public interested in biomedical science, human diseases driven by SLCs, and drug development.

5. External communication of results and dissemination activities

The individual beneficiaries themselves will be the driving force behind the dissemination and internal communication activities within REsolution. They will be supported by the project management team. Given the short duration of the project, REsolution will make use of the dissemination channels established for the RESOLUTE project (e.g. news, website, and social media).

Besides REsolution dissemination activities, we aim to achieve a “multiplier effect” by the engagement of other international scientific networks (such as the International Transmembrane Transporter Society, European Molecular Biology Organization, Federation of European Biochemical Societies, the Gordon Research Conference in membrane transporters community, European Life-science Infrastructure for Biological Information – ELIXIR, the National Centre of Competence in Research TransCure network). This engagement will occur through regular exchange of information and data, collaborations and the participation in conferences organized by these networks.

One of the most important and effective dissemination activities is the publication of the results in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals. A publication plan is outlined in section 5.3.6 to maximise the project impact.

The table below summarizes the foreseen dissemination activities for REsolution:

Activity	Description	Target Audience	Channels
RESOLUTE web portal	REsolution mission and access to resources such as the RESOLUTE knowledgebase and database.	- Scientific community - General public - Policy makers	- re-solute.eu - re-solute.eu/knowledgebase - re-solute.eu/database
Social media	Presence on social media platforms to increase visibility of SLCs in general and the REsolution project in particular	- Scientific community - Clinicians - General public - Policy makers	- Social media (Twitter) - Videos (YouTube)
Scientific publications	Open-access scientific publication by REsolution scientists	- Scientific community (academic, pharma) - Clinicians - Specialist media	- International peer-reviewed scientific journals
Presentation of results	Oral and poster presentations at leading conferences in the field	- Scientific community - Clinicians - General public - Policy makers	- Selected conferences - Selected workshops
Press releases	Addressed to the different stakeholders	- Scientific community - General public - Clinicians - Patients - Policy makers - Media outlets	- Social media - Scientific media platforms - IMI communication office - Videos
Collaborations with patient organizations	Interactions with patient organizations depending on involved disease areas of investigated SLCs	- Patients - General public - Policy makers	- Teleconferences - Newsletters

Collaborations with other consortia	Interactions with other initiatives, (e.g. IMI-FAIRplus, IMI-EUOPEN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific community (academic, pharma) - Clinicians - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Newsletters - Agreements - Teleconferences - Consortium meetings
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5.1. External communication tools

All promotion material generated within the project, including scientific publications and presentations, the project website, etc. will follow the communication guidelines provided by IMI.

- A **‘corporate project design’** (logo, colors, PPT templates etc.) as basic framework for the appearance of the project in the stakeholder community.
- **Promotion materials** such as leaflets, brochures, project posters, slideshows etc. to facilitate presentations at events and to support meetings of project scientists, etc.
- A **project website (<https://re-solute.eu/resolution>)** is the main online access point for the different target groups and which supports and reinforce the rest of the dissemination activities. In an information capacity, the website will highlight project objectives, activities, outcomes and relevant updates. As repository of information, we use the RESOLUTE website, where we will store and make available project resources (including scientific data) and publications to the project participants as well as to the scientific community and the specialized public.
- Use of **social media** will provide areas for exchange on various topics related to SLC research and applications and for raising awareness of the research and its results. The Twitter account [@RESOLUTE IMI](#) is the main social media channel for RESOLUTE and REsolution. A YouTube channel was created for RESOLUTE and REsolution to upload videos. REsolution members use their private LinkedIn accounts to promote REsolution content.
- Project results and activities will also be disseminated on a series of **external databases and websites** for awareness purposes and to foster exchanges on project specific scientific aspects.
- **Press releases** will be addressed to the different stakeholders.
- **Public project handbook** will be released to the public domain in our web page and we plan to have a printed version to distribute among external collaborators.
- **IMI Communications Office** will be engaged for general public outreach activities.
- **REsolution behind the scenes Video Series:** Our goal is to heighten awareness of REsolution. We will do that by creating simple, short video clips of the people behind the project activities. We will distribute them in social media and the web portal. The concept is modular – we will publish one video every 6 months during 2022 / 2023. The table below shows an overview of the planned videos:

Topic	People	Released Dates	Type of work
WP1	WP1 team	Q1 2022	Computational
WP2	WP2 team	Q3 2022	Experimental
WP3	WP3 team	Q1 2023	Computational
WP4	WP4 team	Q3 2023	Computational

5.2. Entities responsible for implementation of the dissemination activities

The individual beneficiaries themselves will be the driving force behind the publishing of data in scientific papers and the presentation of conferences. They will be supported by the PMT if needed, e.g. for the internal pre-publication notification process within the consortium. Decisions on and planning of scientific events, collaborations and hosting of REsolution data on external websites and databases will be made by the EB and GA respectively, with support from the PMT.

5.3. Procedure for the agreement on dissemination of results

The internal procedure for the agreement on dissemination of results aims at ensuring the high quality and value of results. The review and approval process of disseminations will be further outlined in the Consortium Agreement. Furthermore, this process aims at verifying if there are no objections to dissemination by any beneficiaries on the type of dissemination and assures the correct timing for notification and response of the partners. Briefly, the process starts with the notification by email to each beneficiary. The type of dissemination activity with their respective review time are detailed below for each activity, in accordance with the review procedure described in the Consortium Agreement. If a beneficiary agrees with a dissemination activity, no response is required. In case of a conflict of interest, a beneficiary needs to reply within the defined review period and can request to reject or delay dissemination for a defined amount of time, as further detailed below.

5.3.1. REsolution dissemination officers

number / short name	Officer 1	Officer 2
(1) CeMM	Giulio Superti-Furga	Alvaro Ingles-Prieto
(2) UOX	David Sauer	
(3) ULIV	Douglas Kell	Marina Wright-Muelas
(4) AXXAM	Lia Scarabottolo	Sara Tremolada
(5) ULEI	Laura Heitman	Ad IJzerman
(6) MPIMR	Kai Johnsson	Philipp Leippe
(7) UNIVIE	Gerhard Ecker	Claire Colas
(8) Pfizer	Claire Steppan	Anders Malarstig
(9) Bayer	Alexander Ehrmann	Aidan MacNamara

5.3.2. Types of dissemination and corresponding internal review period

Type of dissemination	Internal review period
Scientific publications	35 days advance notification / 30 days review period
Abstract submission for conference	15 days
Scientific talk (conference / invited talk) with novel or published data	15 days
Poster presentation with novel or published data	15 days
Scientific outreach / interview, external newsletter	7 days
Promotion material	15 days
Protocols, SOPs, etc.	15 days
Reagents	15 days
Data	30 days
Reporting of deliverables to IMI	15 days
Annual report to IMI	7 days

These terms were approved by voting on the General Assembly meeting on October 22nd, 2021. The internal review periods might be modified by GA if necessary.

5.3.3. Notification of beneficiaries

- All REsolution beneficiaries are notified about a planned dissemination activity.
- Email with detailed description of the activity is directed to the REsolution dissemination officers. They should find suitable internal reviewers in the organization, who are competent to access quality, interpretation and scientific validity of particular dissemination entity.

- Sharing the actual dissemination entity is performed via dedicated SharePoint.
- For minor disseminations (e.g. abstract, poster, slides for presentation), it is possible to share the dissemination entity as a draft for internal review – however the final version has to be distributed among all the beneficiaries later.

5.3.4. Response by beneficiaries

- Every beneficiary has a veto during the defined review period.
- If a beneficiary agrees with a dissemination activity, no response is required.
- In case of a conflict of interest, a beneficiary should reply within the defined review period.
- Beneficiary can request to delay a dissemination for the time required to resolve issues related to confidentiality, intellectual property, data quality or other.
- Minor objections can be directly resolved with the objecting participant.
- Major objections requiring a significant adaptation of the dissemination activity effectively restart the dissemination process.

5.3.5. Quality and validity of results

Quality of data is the highest priority for RESOLTE, therefore

- Dissemination officers should find reviewers within their organization to evaluate particular dissemination entity;
- Any beneficiary is encouraged to respond, if there are concerns on data quality, interpretation or scientific validity;
- Any beneficiary should also notify the publishing party if there are additional or novel data available that would support the current publication or argue against it.

5.3.6. Scientific publication plan

One of the most important and effective dissemination activities is the publication of the results that are generated by REsolution in peer-reviewed journals. We envisage the publications in the following directions:

- Publication of benchmarking of Variant Effect Predictors (VEPs)
- Publication(s) on Deep Mutagenesis Scanning (DMS) studies
- Publication on structural and functional characterization of individual SLC variants
- Publication on optimized VEP for SLCs

6. Knowledge management and protection

Knowledge Management and protection of results is defined in the REsolution Consortium Agreement and will be monitored from the beginning of the project. The Consortium Agreement will manage amongst other things the ownership and access to key knowledge.

- **Agreement on confidentiality among participants and towards external parties:** The consortium will ensure that dissemination of results will be in line with possibly existing confidentiality obligations. Shared data will be labelled as 'confidential' or 'non-confidential'. Additional appropriate legal agreements will be put in place as, e.g. allowing bilateral access to confidential data, for a specified purpose and subject to special conditions. However, as a general principle, most information and data

will be made freely available to the consortium and, when appropriate and quality-controlled, made available to the public.

- **Agreement on dissemination of results:** Each beneficiary shall disseminate its results as soon as possible, unless such dissemination goes against its legitimate interests based on a defined internal review and approval process that is regulated by the REsolution CA.
- **Agreement on background:** During the project, the beneficiaries enjoy, unless prevented or restricted from doing so by obligations to others, access rights to the background of the other beneficiaries to the extent necessary for undertaking and completing the project as well as required for the purpose of the research use of results under fair and reasonable conditions. Background for each beneficiary has been defined in the REsolution CA
- **Agreement on ownership of and access to project results:** During and after the completion of the project, beneficiaries and their affiliated entities enjoy access rights to the project results for research use under royalty-free conditions; after completion of the project, third parties have the right to request access rights to the results for research use under fair and reasonable conditions.

7. Data management

A data management plan (DMP) will detail guidelines on managing research data generated or collected during the project. The initial version of the DMP will be published in month 6 (D3.1), and it is intended to be a living document which will be updated throughout the project whenever significant changes occur.

8. Internal communication and data sharing activities

The REsolution internal communication strategy ensures efficient interaction and rapid data sharing between partners. Special attention will be given to internal communication (i.e. clear information on the progress within and between WPs). Activities and channels for REsolution internal communication are summarized in the table below and will be aligned with the channels used in RESOLUTE. REsolution beneficiaries will have full access to RESOLUTE results. However, REsolution will create independent internal communication channels to ensure confidentiality prior to data release.

Activity	Description	Target Audience	Channels
File sharing	Exchange, collect and update documents, protocols and other information in a fast and flexible way	REsolution beneficiaries	Microsoft Office365 SharePoint
Email groups	Work package specific discussions and exchange of ideas	REsolution beneficiaries	Microsoft Office365 Groups
Monthly Teleconferences	Update on scientific progress of each WP	REsolution beneficiaries	Microsoft Teams / Zoom /
Satellite meetings during RESOLUTE consortium meeting	Present the global status or discuss focused topics	REsolution beneficiaries	Conferences
Chat rooms	Share and discuss information within and across WPs	REsolution beneficiaries	Microsoft Teams
Data sharing and interpretation	Access to datasets and interactive dashboards of data generated by REsolution and before public release	REsolution beneficiaries	Web portal

9. Training program for junior researchers

The REsolution beneficiaries will benefit from the RESOLUTE Training Programme, which aims at training scientists of all levels of seniority, but particularly PhD students, postdocs and research associates, to be

recognized as SLC experts in the decades to come in pharma, academia and newly founded companies. This program will as well enlarge their professional network, which will result in increase of their job market value.

10. Appendix - Abbreviations

CA	Consortium agreement
DEP	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
DMS	Deep Mutagenesis Scanning
EB	Executive board
EMA	European Medicines Agency
FDA	U. S. Food and Drug Administration
GA	General Assembly
PMT	Project management team
SLC	Solute carrier
VEP	Variant Effect Predictors
WP	Work package